

FOOD ALLERGY IN YOUNG CHILDREN: APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.

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The article is devoted to food allergies are a major cause of allergic diseases in children during the first years of life. Represented the etiological structure of food allergy, described her clinical symptoms. Covering issues of nutritional status of children with food allergy and its methods of diagnosis.

Keywords: food allergy, children, diagnosis, diet.

Annotation. Food allergy is one of the important problems of modern pediatrics, since it often occurs in the first months of a child's life and has a great influence on the development of severe allergic diseases in older age. The highest frequency of food allergies is observed in children of the first years of life and is 6-8%. (1) Food allergy is a state of hypersensitivity to food products, which is based on immunological mechanisms, the leading ones of which are IgE-mediated reactions (2). Almost any food product can cause the development of food allergies. Currently, more than 160 food allergens have been identified that cause IgE-mediated allergic reactions in children. The "big eight" products with the greatest allergenicity include cow's milk, eggs, fish, wheat, peanuts, soy, crustaceans (shrimp, crabs, lobsters, etc.), nuts (hazelnuts, almonds, walnuts).

Common allergens include cocoa and chocolate, citrus fruits, strawberries, wild strawberries, honey, animal and poultry meat, caviar and other seafood, and cereals. Cow's milk is the most common cause of food allergies in young children, especially in the first year of life (1, 3). Cow's milk contains more than 20 antigens, among which β -lactoglobulin and casein have the greatest allergenic activity. Some whey proteins (α -lactalbumin, bovine immunoglobulin, bovine serum albumin) are destroyed by boiling, while β -lactoglobulin is heat-stable. Casein also changes slightly during heat treatment, and precipitates when souring, which is why it is especially abundant in cheeses. It is known that among children in the first year of life, allergy to cow's milk proteins (CMP) is more common in children who are bottle-fed (2-7%) (4).

The development of milk allergy in them is facilitated by the unreasonably early introduction of various milk formulas, including non-adapted ones, as well as the premature (at 2-3 months and earlier) prescription of milk porridges, especially in

children genetically predisposed to atopy. This may be due to the mother's excessive consumption of dairy products during pregnancy, which contributes to the formation of intrauterine sensitization, as well as the use of milk formulas for supplementary feeding in the first days of life after the birth of the child, excessive consumption of milk and dairy products by the mother during breastfeeding. In the future, each newly introduced food protein (cereals, vegetables, meat, eggs, fish, etc.) is a new potential allergen that can contribute to the development of allergic reactions, especially in the first months of the child's life, when the immune and enzymatic systems of the gastrointestinal tract are not yet mature enough. A highly allergenic product is chicken egg white, as well as eggs of other types of poultry. Often, an allergy to chicken egg whites is combined with intolerance to chicken meat and broth. A common cause of exacerbations of allergic diseases is fish, so it is not recommended to give it to children of the first year of life if there are signs of atopy.

Fish allergens are heat-stable and are practically not destroyed during cooking. Most children react to all types of fish, but allergies to sea fish are more common than to river fish. It has been established that the degree of sensitization to fish proteins does not decrease with age and persists in adults. Allergic reactions are possible when eating seafood (caviar, shrimp, crayfish, lobsters, oysters, etc.). Food products of plant origin are also of significant importance in the development of allergic reactions in children. Proteins of cereal grains, primarily wheat and rye, and less often rice, oats, buckwheat, have pronounced allergenic activity. In children of the first year of life, soy products can cause the occurrence or exacerbation of atopic dermatitis and gastrointestinal manifestations of allergy. This is due to the widespread use of soy and its derivatives in the food industry as substitutes for milk and dairy products, meat, as well as additives in confectionery and sausage products, sauces, which are common in the diet of the population, including pregnant and lactating women.

The aim of the study: to study food allergies in young children: approaches to diagnosis and treatment. The clinical manifestations of food allergies are varied, since various organs and systems can be involved in the pathological process and there may be multiple organ pathology. For young children, the most typical are skin manifestations of food allergies, and among them, atopic dermatitis (5). In this period, it is characterized by the predominance of the exudative form. The first manifestations of the disease usually appear in the 2nd-3rd month of life in the form of transient hyperemia in the cheek area. Against the background of hyperemia, small itchy vesicles with serous contents subsequently appear, which open with the formation of superficial erosions, areas of weeping appear, covered with serous and serous-hemorrhagic crusts. This entire clinical picture is accompanied by severe itching. With a localized process, the skin of the face is affected with the exception of the nasolabial triangle.

Research methods. In the common variant, the process affects the skin of the trunk, extensor surfaces of the upper and lower extremities. By 1.5-2 years, the exudative form turns into erythematous-squamous. The skin becomes dry, itchy papules appear, tending to merge with the formation of foci of infiltration. Typical sites of localization of the process are the flexor surfaces of the forearms, shins, elbow and popliteal fossa, dorsal surfaces of the hands. Acute urticaria is a common manifestation of food allergy in children. Clinically, urticaria is characterized by the appearance of

itchy blistering rashes of various shapes and sizes. Against the background of urticaria, angioedema (Quincke's edema) can develop on the eyelids, lips, and auricles. In some cases, urticaria may develop with direct skin contact with a food product (cow's milk, fish, nuts, eggs) in a sensitized patient. Symptoms of damage to the digestive organs are the second most common manifestations of food allergies (6).

They are usually combined with skin lesions and manifest as vomiting, nausea, abdominal pain, diarrhea. At the same time, symptoms of food allergies may already appear in the maternity hospital in the case of the prescription of mixtures based on cow's milk. The clinical picture of damage to the gastrointestinal tract depends on the level of localization of allergic inflammation and may manifest itself as symptoms of gastritis, gastroenteritis, enterocolitis, colitis. Symptoms of allergy may develop immediately after the food allergen enters the oral cavity in the form of itching, swelling of the tongue, lips, mucous membrane of the oral cavity. In children in the first months of life, an allergic process in the esophagus (allergic esophagitis) may resemble the clinical picture of pylorospasm and be accompanied by severe pain during meals.

Allergic intestinal lesion may have a different clinical picture. The mildest form occurs in the form of intestinal colic, which in children in the first months of life occurs several weeks after the start of artificial feeding with milk formulas. In this case, the child is restless, cries after feeding. In more severe forms, infants may experience vomiting, bloating, frequent loose stools with a large amount of mucus and even blood. The most common food products that cause allergic intestinal lesions in children in the first year of life are cow's milk and soy. After eliminating the food allergen from the diet, stool normalizes. Respiratory tract damage as a manifestation of food allergy is less common in young children and usually does not occur in isolation, but in combination with damage to the skin and gastrointestinal tract. Clinically, respiratory pathology in food allergy manifests itself as bronchial asthma and allergic rhinitis and can be caused by sensitization to fish and egg allergens.

Results of the study. Specific diagnostics of food allergies in children is based on the assessment of the allergological anamnesis, clinical picture, and the results of allergological and laboratory tests. The most significant method for diagnosing food allergies is anamnesis. Allergy anamnesis allows us to clarify the range of suspected food allergens, their connection with the occurrence of certain clinical manifestations, the duration of the time interval between the intake of products and the occurrence of clinical symptoms. Taking into account the possibility of intrauterine sensitization and sensitization through breast milk, the nutritional characteristics of the pregnant and nursing mother, the presence of dietary disorders, especially excessive consumption of any food products are determined. It is important to study the child's diet: establish the timing of the introduction of food products (juices, complementary foods), the time of transition to mixed and artificial feeding and compare them with the timing of the appearance of symptoms from the skin or other organs (gastrointestinal tract, respiratory organs, ENT organs), which allows in most cases to identify the "culprit" food product. A food diary can be of significant help in identifying causative food products. A food diary should be kept constantly for several weeks, noting the days and hours of intake of any food products, the composition of these products, their

quantity, and then in a separate column, record changes in the child's condition and the time of appearance of certain signs of the disease.

Analysis of the information presented in the diary allows you to identify the "culprit" food allergen and, based on this, prescribe a diagnostic elimination diet with the exclusion of the suspected food product. With the correct identification of the allergenic product and its elimination from the diet, remission of the disease occurs. In addition to the anamnesis and diagnostic elimination diet, skin tests (scarification or prick tests) are used in the diagnosis of food allergies. But they are carried out during the period of remission of the allergic disease and only in the allergy room under the supervision of an allergist.

Their diagnostic significance is assessed in comparison with the anamnesis data. A positive skin test with a food allergen with positive allergy anamnesis data confirms the presence of food sensitization in the child. Along with skin tests, laboratory tests are of great importance in the specific diagnosis of food allergies, including the determination of specific immunoglobulins of class E to food allergens in serum using the radioimmunological or enzyme immunoassay method (1, 3). The use of laboratory tests is preferable in cases where skin tests are impossible (widespread skin process, severe or systemic reactions to food in the anamnesis, long-term use of antihistamines, etc.). The Institute has accumulated significant experience in laboratory diagnostics of food sensitization in young children. using immunoblotting options (Rida test system, Allergy Screen, Allergodip), as well as our own version of allergy diagnostics, which combines "battery screening" with the advantages of ELISA, using liquid biotylated allergens from various manufacturers - "Doctor Fuke", S.A.R.L.A., "Alkor-Bio". The analyzed data of studies of specific IgE (n=148) in children aged 1 month to 3 years using immunoblot (group 1, n=80) and classical ELISA using biotylated allergens.

The significance of a particular food allergen in the development of the disease can be considered proven if the results of skin tests and/or laboratory tests match the anamnesis data and the results of diagnostic elimination diets. In doubtful cases, an oral provocation test is performed to confirm the anamnesis data. A positive result of a provocation test with a food allergen is an indication for excluding this product from the child's diet. Diet therapy is the most important component of the complex treatment of children with food allergies, since it is a pathogenetic method of treatment. Properly structured nutrition allows you to reduce the antigen load on the child's body, contributes to the rapid achievement and maintenance of remission of the disease. Therapeutic nutrition for children of the first years of life suffering from food allergies is built on an individual plan, based on the clinical manifestations of allergy, the spectrum of identified sensitization, age, nutritional status of the child, the functional state of the digestive organs, as well as the nature of previous feeding. The diet for food allergies is based primarily on the principle of elimination.

During the period of clinical manifestations of the disease, the diet should be as strict as possible and provide, on the one hand, for the exclusion of causative and cross-reacting allergens and products with high sensitizing activity, and on the other, for adequate replacement of the eliminated products with others that are non-allergenic for the patient. During the remission stage, the child's diet is gradually expanded by previously excluded products and dishes. At the same time, regardless of the period of

the disease, the diet should provide the child's physiological needs for basic food ingredients, vitamins and microelements. In cases of food allergy detection in children who are breastfed, given the unique properties of breast milk, it is necessary to keep it in the child's diet as long as possible, preferably at least until 6 months of age. A nursing woman is prescribed a hypoallergenic diet, while the degree of restrictions and the set of eliminated products are quite individual and depend primarily on the spectrum of causative allergens and the severity of the clinical manifestations of allergy in the child. It is recommended to exclude from the diet of a nursing mother highly allergenic products: fish, caviar, seafood (crayfish, crabs, shrimp, crab sticks), eggs, mushrooms, nuts, honey, chocolate, coffee, cocoa, as well as broths, hot spices, onions, garlic, radishes, products containing dyes, preservatives, carbonated drinks.

If the child has an allergy to cow's milk proteins, milk and dairy products are completely excluded from the nursing mother's diet. In these cases, it is advisable for nursing mothers to use specialized products based on soy protein isolate or goat's milk (if this is not accompanied by an exacerbation of the child's allergy). The amount of cereals and pasta, wheat bread, sugar is reduced by 20-25%, salt - by 30% (7). A hypoallergenic diet is prescribed for nursing mothers for the entire period of breastfeeding. At the same time, it is necessary to ensure a high nutritional and biological value of her diet due to sufficient intake of animal protein, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, which is a prerequisite for maintaining lactation. To enrich the mother's diet, vitamin and mineral complexes, calcium supplements, and products with probiotic properties should be used. The most difficult problem is the organization of nutrition for children in the first year of life with an allergy to cow's milk proteins who are bottle-fed. The main task in these cases is the correct choice of a therapeutic hypoallergenic formula and complementary foods. According to modern recommendations, it is most advisable to prescribe formulas based on highly hydrolyzed milk protein to children suffering from an allergy to cow's milk proteins and who are bottle-fed (8, 9). Hydrolyzed formulas are obtained by breaking down protein molecules by heat and/or enzymatic treatment into peptides and free amino acids, which reduces the allergenic properties of the formula.

The higher the degree of hydrolysis, the lower the antigenicity of the formula. After hydrolysis, the mixture of peptides and amino acids is purified from undigested molecules and their fragments by ultrafiltration and treatment with sorbents. Compared with cow's milk proteins, which have a molecular weight of 10 to 60 kDa, the allergenicity of the protein component of products created on the basis of highly hydrolyzed protein is reduced by 10,000-100,000 times. However, residual amounts of protein antigens may also be preserved in their composition. All hydrolyzed mixtures are enriched with a complex of microelements, vitamins, essential amino acids and meet the WHO requirements for the composition of nutrients for feeding children of the first year of life. Thus, modern hydrolysates are adapted and complete substitutes for breast milk. In recent years, a large selection of hydrolyzed mixtures has appeared on the domestic market. Unfortunately, the choice of a hydrolyzed mixture in a specific clinical situation often causes difficulties for a practicing physician. To do this, you should know the main characteristics of hydrolysates.

Conclusions: Of the fruits, preference is given to green and white apples (Antonov, Semerenko, white filling). Taking into account individual tolerance, pears, white and red currants, yellow and red cherries, yellow plums or baby juices and purees from them are used. Heat treatment of fruits and berries reduces their allergenicity. Cottage cheese, eggs and fish are not introduced into the diet of children with food allergies in the first year of life or are completely eliminated.

List of references:

1. Salomova, F. I., Mirrakhimova, M. K., & Kobilzhonova, S. R. (2022, April). Influence of environmental factors on the development of atopic dermatitis in children. *European journal of science archives conferences series*.
2. Закирходжаев, Ш. Я., & Паттахова, М. Х. (2023). Коррекция диетического питания пациентов с заболеваниями печени после перенесенного Covid-19 с применением местных продуктов.
3. Jalolov, N. N., Sultonov, E. Y., Imamova, A. O., & Oblokulov, A. G. (2023). Main factors of overweight and obesity in children. *Science Promotion*, 1(2), 2-4.
4. Зокирхужаев, Ш. Я., Рустамова, М. Т., Паттахова, М. Х., Нарзиев, Н. М., Жалолов, Н. Н., & Муталов, С. Б. (2023). Коронавирус инфекцияси ва жигар зарарланиши.
5. Ниязова, О. А., Саломова, Ф. И., & Ахмадалиева, Н. О. (2022). Изучение изменений состояния здоровья школьников возникающих при неправильной посадке.
6. Миррахимова, М. Х., Нишонбоева, Н. Ю., & Кобилжонова, Ш. Р. (2022). Атопик дерматит билан касалланган болаларда панкреатик етишмовчиликни коррекциялаш.
7. Саломова, Ф. И. (2009). Функциональное состояние опорно-двигательного аппарата школьников с нарушениями осанки. *Травматология и ортопедия России*, (1), 70-73.
8. Шеркузиева, Г. Ф., Саломова, Ф. И., & Юлдашева, Ф. У. (2023). Результаты санитарно-химических исследований воды.
9. Ярмухамедова, Н. Ф., & Бакиева, Ш. Х. (2021). Features of the Frequency of Distribution of Alleles and Genotypes of Polymorphisms of the Gene Tnf-A (G-308a) in patients with Rhinosinusitis and the Assessment of Their Role....
10. Akhmadaliev, N. O., Imamova, A. O., Niyazova, O. A., Muratbayeva, A. P., & Umarov, B. A. (2023). HYGIENIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HARMFUL FACTORS OF WORKING CONDITIONS OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES DOCTORS.
11. Ниязова, О., & Саломова, Ф. (2022). Studying changes in the health state of school children arising from incorrect fitting.
12. Abduqodirova, L. K., Imamova, A. O., & Niyozova, O. A. (2022). Методы оценки функционального состояния организма при выполнении умственной работы.
13. Akhmadaliev, N. O., Imamova, A. O., Niyazova, O. A., Muratbayeva, A. P., & Umarov, B. A. (2023). HYGIENIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HARMFUL FACTORS OF WORKING CONDITIONS OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES DOCTORS.

14. Imamova, A. O. (2023). Studying the health of frequently ill children of preschool age and methods for forming a healthy lifestyle.
15. DS, K. S. R. X. (2022, May). PREVALENCE OF ALLERGIC DISEASES IN CHILDREN UNDER HOT CLIMATIC CONDITIONS. Materials of International Scientific-Practical Conference. «Only English: Topical Issues of Healthcare».
16. Ibodullaevna, S. F., Rustamovna, K. S., Gairatovna, A. D., & Abdurakhmonovna, S. H. (2022). PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF ALLERGIC DISEASES IN CHILDREN IN HOT CLIMATIC CONDITIONS. *Art of Medicine. International Medical Scientific Journal*, 2(3).
17. Akhmadalievna, N., Nigmatullaeva, D., Kamilov, A., Hakimova, D., & Salomova, F. (2020). Comparative self-assessment of the teachers' health of higher education institutions of the republic of Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(5), 1353-1355.
18. Ниязова, О. А., Ахмадалиева, Н. О., Валиулин, Р. И., & Болтаев, М. М. (2022). *Comparative assessment of nutrition of university students of medical and non-medical profile* (Doctoral dissertation, European multidisciplinary journal of modern science).
19. Imamova, A. O., & Soliyeva, L. O. (2022). *Hygienic assessment of children's health in the orphanage* (Doctoral dissertation, «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ» Xalqaro ilmiy jurnal).
20. Зокирхўжаев, Ш. Я., Рустамова, М. Т., Паттахова, М. Х., Жалолов, Н. Н., & Муталов, С. Б. (2023). Сурункали жигар касалликларида соғлом овқатланишнинг ахамияти.
21. Саломова, Ф. И., & Тошматова, Г. О. (2012). Эпидемиология мастопатии и особенности заболеваемости женщин, страдающих мастопатией. *Врач-аспирант*, 52(3.1), 222-228.
22. Jalolov, N. N., Sobirov, O. G., Kabilzhonova, S. R., & Imamova, A. O. (2023). The role of a healthy lifestyle in the prevention of myocardial infarction.
23. Otajonov, I., Shaykhova, G., Salomova, F., Kurbanova, K., Kurbonov, K., & Malokhat, N. (2020). Effectiveness of diet in experimental chronic kidney disease. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(2), 1097-1109.
24. Qizi, A. M. X., & O'G'Li, J. N. N. (2023). Jismoniy faollik orqali stressni boshqarish. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 13(1), 19-20.
25. Rahimov, B. B., Salomova, F. I., Jalolov, N. N., Sulstonov, E. Y., & Obloqulov, A. G. (2023). О 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI NAVOIY SHAHRI HAVO SIFATINI BAHOLASH: MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIM YOLLARI.
26. Salomova, F. I., Akhmadalievna, N. O., Sadullayeva Kh, A., Imamova, A. O., & Nigmatullayeva, D. Z. (2023). Hygienic characteristics of the social portrait, conditions and lifestyle of infectious diseases doctors.
27. Ниязова, О. А., & Валиулин, Р. И. (2022). *Изучение и гигиеническая оценка фактического питания студентов* (Doctoral dissertation, Молодежный инновационный вестник. Научно-практический журнал Том 11).